

Stress Among Adolescents: Roles and Responsibilities of Parents and Teachers

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Abstract

Being literate does not guarantee a successful transition to independent living. In today's environment, learning to learn and the desire to unlearn and adapt based on circumstances, as well as relearn new abilities, are crucial means of transformation in achieving higher levels of excellence for a successful life. Beyond reading, writing, and arithmetic, a child's capacity to manage this increasingly complicated world necessitates a diverse combination of cognitive, social, and practical skills. Around the world, Life Skills-Based Education is being used to empower young people in difficult situations. Life Skill-Based Education is an interactive teaching and learning method that allows students to acquire knowledge while developing attitudes and skills that encourage adopting healthy behaviour. There is an urgent need to establish life skills education for young people. Developing life skills enables teenagers to translate their knowledge, attitudes, and health behaviour. However, our educational requirements are becoming increasingly severe at all levels of education, and students are enduring significant stress. This research focuses on stress management in teenagers from the perspective of Life Skills Education, as well as how a teacher and parents can assist adolescents in coping with stress on an ongoing basis. As a result, children and adolescents must have the opportunity to develop life skills that will assist them in adequately coping with daily challenges and important life events.

Keywords: *Life Skills, Role of Parents and Teachers, Management of Stress, Adolescents*

Introduction

More than merely possessing literacy skills is required to guarantee a smooth transition to self-sufficiency. In the modern world, attaining greater degrees of excellence for a successful livelihood requires an individual to learn new things and be prepared to unlearn, alter, and relearn new skills in response to circumstances. Not everyone can become an expert in every one of them, but one should aim to become knowledgeable in as many as they can. In the contemporary world, when globalisation and competition have become fashionable terms, a person's education or experience alone is insufficient to guarantee efficient operation. A child must possess a wide range of cognitive, social, and practical skills to navigate this increasingly complicated world, in addition to reading, writing, and math skills.

Life Skills-Based Education (LSBE) is used worldwide to empower youth in difficult circumstances. The term "LSBE" describes an interactive teaching and learning process that helps students gain knowledge, attitudes and skills that encourage the adoption of healthy

behaviours. To navigate the ups and downs of life and solve the jigsaw puzzle of complex situations with ease, one has to possess certain life skills. "Abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enables individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life" is how the World Health Organisation (WHO) defines life skills. Delors' four pillars of learning—learning to know, learning to do, learning to be, and learning to coexist—form the foundation of the International Bureau of Education's (IBE) conceptual framework. Life skills have become a much-needed but sometimes overlooked subject in correctional education in recent years. The issues that today's kids must deal with include poverty, discrimination, disease, violence, and environmental destruction. A wide range of psychological and social abilities known as "life skills" can support kids in making wise decisions, communicating, interacting with others, and navigating their environment. By incorporating life skills into the core of our educational programmes, we provide kids with the tools they need to overcome obstacles and confidently navigate the world. The 164

countries committed to Education for All have recognised the vital necessity of life skills and have made them a required learning goal for all teenagers and young adults. Today, at least 70 developing nations include life skills education in their formal curricula. Children have an inalienable right to a high-quality education that upholds their dignity, broadens their opportunities for leading fulfilling lives, and helps them change the society in which they live.

Need for Life Skills in Education

Secondary education is a critical time for a student's physical, mental, and psychological development. Given this, children must receive life skills education because they do not yet possess the knowledge and skills necessary to deal with challenges in the real world. Because of peer pressure and the increasingly competitive society, life skills training has become vital. In contrast to previous educational approaches that focused solely on one particular subject, life skills-based learning incorporates assessing the student's skills and providing tools and resources to help them develop. Even a cursory look at our current and expanding youth population reveals that social issues, conflict, violence, and discrimination based on gender and ethnicity are serious concerns. Adolescents who develop life skills can better convert their knowledge, attitudes, and health behaviours. Examples include learning to minimise risky behaviours and replace them with healthy ones that will enhance their lives. The following results have been attained via life skills: Reduced aggression; enhanced pro-social conduct; diminished negative, self-destructive conduct; enhanced capacity to organise and select efficient problem-solving strategies; enhanced self-perception, self-awareness, social and affective adaptation, etc.

Essential life Skills

Problem-solving, critical thinking, effective communication, decision-making, creative thinking, interpersonal relationship skills, self-awareness building, empathy, and coping with stress and emotions are the ten core life skill strategies and techniques listed by UNICEF, UNESCO, and WHO. The World Health

Organisation (WHO) divides life skills into the following three components:

Decision-making and Critical thinking abilities

Critical thinking and decision-making abilities involve gathering information, making decisions, and solving problems. A person must also be able to assess how their current behaviours and those of others may affect them in the future. They must be able to weigh the pros and cons of different approaches and the impact of their and other people's values.

Communication & interpersonal abilities

Interpersonal/communication skills: these comprise both spoken and unspoken conversation, attentive listening, feeling-expression, and feedback-giving abilities. Assertiveness and negotiation/refusal skills directly impacting one's capacity to handle conflict also included in this category? A crucial interpersonal skill is empathy, which is the capacity to pay attention to and comprehend the needs of others. Respect for people in our immediate vicinity is necessary for cooperation and teamwork. Adolescents' ability to acquire this skill set helps them fit in with society. These abilities lead to the acceptance of social norms, which serve as the basis for social behaviour in adulthood.

Resilience and self-control abilities

The term "coping and self-management skills" refers to abilities that heighten one's sense of internal control and convince one that one can influence change and change the world. The broader self-management skills include self-worth, self-awareness, self-evaluation abilities, and goal-setting proficiency. The person learns to deal with anger, sadness, and anxiety, as well as how to deal with tragedy or loss. Stress and time management are as important as positive thinking and relaxation techniques.

Concept of Stress

Students worldwide are under great stress at school as the criteria for education become more rigorous at all educational levels. Stress is the body's reaction to any demands made, and it can affect us positively or negatively. The majority

of the time, people discuss the bad aspects of expectations that interfere with our well-being and give us discomfort. Demands can originate internally (from our thoughts) or externally (from other people, places, objects, and situations). The latter is the main reason that any of us should be distressed. We react to the demands in different ways: psychologically (worry, anxiety, guilt, poor concentration, racing thoughts), behaviourally (increased smoking, alcohol and drug use, compulsive eating, nail-biting, reckless behaviour), and physiologically (increased heart rate, sweating, rapid and shallow breathing, muscle tightness). Children and teenagers experience stress and anxiety at the same rates as adults. The main causes of stress in childhood and adolescence are demanding familial responsibilities, abused or deprived childhoods, high expectations in academic or other performances, stressed-out and careless parents, and growing up tensions. Children frequently experience stress because of their parents' lack of effective coping mechanisms or lack of emotional availability for them. Children who are under stress may exhibit emotional disorders, violent conduct, shyness, social anxiety, and a general lack of interest in activities that they might normally find fun. According to research, kids who are made to live on too adult levels sometimes grow against following their parents' (or society's) laws. These kids frequently react aggressively and indignantly to stimuli.

Sources of Stress among Adolescents: In reaction to a range of growing-up anxieties, many teenagers tend to become nonconformists and become victims of teenage depression. On the other hand, children's performances suffer on a variety of levels when stress causes them to experience anxieties and anxiety. Teens' daily stressors most frequently come from:

- Problems with peers (e.g., being bullied, break-up with boyfriend or girlfriend, dating relationship problems) Family issues or problems with parents
- School-related problems or pressures: Their thoughts, feelings, or behaviours (feeling depressed or lonely)

- Death of a loved one
- Prolonged illness or serious issues in the family
- Relocating to a different neighbourhood or school
- Taking up excessive workloads or unrealistic goals
- A family's financial issues Unsafe living environment/neighbourhood
- Academic pressure and career decisions
- Pressure to wear certain types of clothing or hairstyles
- Pressure to try drugs, alcohol or sex
- Adaptation to bodily changes

Coping with Stress

Understanding the origins of stress in our lives, how it affects us, and taking actions to assist in managing our stress levels are all part of coping with stress. This could entail changing our physical surroundings or way of life, for example, to lessen the causes of stress. Alternatively, it can entail developing relaxation techniques to prevent health issues from arising from tensions brought on by inevitable stress. There are a few skills for managing stress-

- Time management
- Positive thinking
- Relaxation techniques

Role of a Teacher:

Teachers are no longer the only people who can impart knowledge and information. Whether in more adaptable community-based programmes or in traditional schools, teachers are vital to the advancement of high-quality education. They are change agents and champions for change. Without the ownership and active involvement of teachers, no education change is likely to be successful. In addition, educators need to acknowledge their professional obligations and take accountability towards students and communities. The strategies should cover the new role that educators must play in educating pupils for the rapidly changing, technology-driven, knowledge-based economy. To create

engaging, interactive learning environments, teachers must recognise the range of students' learning styles and their intellectual and physical maturation. It takes professionally qualified and skilled individuals from within the nation to administer life skill education efficiently.

- Must be able to comprehend the variability of students' intellectual and physical growth as well as their learning preferences.
- Implement practical tools and materials to identify causes of stress.
- Methods include brainstorming, role-playing, games and discussions, case studies, and working in small groups and pairs.
- Regular conversations with the students to learn about their stress levels and provide guidance in the role of a counsellor.
- Handling the pupils with empathy to prevent harm. Introduce them to different levels of stress management approaches.
- Talk to their parents and friends about the issues. Don't pressurise the students to do anything which they don't want to do.
- Help students explore their identities
- Train pupils in life skills with the assistance of professionals

Role of Parents

Parents can help their teens in the following ways:

- Encourage your adolescent to share their experiences and show that you are prepared to listen. Don't just make snap judgments and offer suggestions. Depending on the circumstances, your teen could simply want to be understood rather than seek guidance. For your youngster, a problem could appear insignificant, but it could be of great concern. Saying "you'll get over it" or downplaying an issue is ineffective. It conveys a message you are either unwilling to listen to or do not comprehend.
- Provide comfort, inspiration, and assistance. Don't give up if your adolescent is agitated or rejects your attempts to console them, even if you are ready to offer verbal or physical

support. These responses to stress are typical. Have patience and let your child know that you are there for them whenever they need you.

- Motivate your adolescent to engage in things they typically enjoy
- Encourage participation in constructive and pro-social endeavours set a good example for coping and stress management techniques.
- Establish a rapport with your adolescent so that he or she will feel at ease approaching you for assistance.
- Avoid bringing up your troubles with them.
- Conversely, talk to kids about the family's objectives and have cordial conversations about challenges.
- Try not to assign your child an excessive amount of homework or extracurricular activities after school.
- Let kids discover how to set their own pace.
- Don't enrol them in every course that is offered, and don't hold yourself to a high standard in everything.

Conclusion

One can strive towards more positive and comprehensive approaches to education by teaching life skills to the next generation and the generations after them. To put it briefly, sharing well, caring well, and faring well are the cornerstones of life skills. You must possess life skills to succeed in both your personal and professional life. Too much emphasis on scientific and technological developments and their impact on students has left behind human development qualitatively, which is now influencing youngsters adversely. However, the inclusion of life skills will diffuse the situation positively. By integrating life skills into the school curriculum, the learning process becomes more effective. Given that life skills are crucial to a child's development of a balanced personality, let's find ways both inside and outside of the classroom to instil the spirit of real-life values in the minds of the younger generation as it grows. Every educational endeavour in the future will need to consider

whether and to what degree it supports learning activities that aid in the development of life skills necessary for overcoming major obstacles in life and ensuring one's survival, as well as the extent to which it fosters the necessary attitudes and motivations (curiosity, interest, and self-starting qualities) for lifelong learning. Life skills cannot be learnt in an abstract and

theoretical manner; instead, individuals must subject their own experiences, circumstances, and observations regarding difficulties to creative analysis and evaluation, as well as collect, examine, and share their experiences in real life .

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